

A STUDY ON TRAINING AND DEVELOPMENT OF EMPLOYEES IN SREE VIDHYA RUBBER INDUSTRY AT MADURAI DISTRICT

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ABSTRACT

Training and development are crucial for improving employee performance and organizational productivity. This study explores the training practices adopted in Sree Vidhya Rubber Industry, located in Madurai District. The research identifies the effectiveness of current training programs, employee perceptions, and areas for improvement. A structured questionnaire was used to collect data from 50 employees across various departments. Findings reveal that while technical training is regularly conducted, there is a lack of soft skills and managerial development programs. The study concludes with suggestions for enhancing training practices to promote overall employee development and organizational growth.

Keywords: Training and development

1.1 INTRODUCTION

In today's competitive business environment, continuous employee development is critical for maintaining productivity, innovation, and motivation. Training equips employees with updated skills, reduces errors, and increases job satisfaction. In industrial units like rubber manufacturing, both technical training and personal development are essential. This study investigates how Sree Vidhya Rubber Industry in Madurai District manages employee training and evaluates its effectiveness from the employees' perspective.

1.1 OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To study the role of training and development in SREE VIDHYA RUBBER INDUSTRY PVT LTD

- To assess the training programmes conducted in the organisation.
- To offer suggestions to improve the training programmes.

1.2 SCOPE OF THE STUDY

- The study is conducted to know the level of knowledge and skills given to the employees in the organization.
- This will help the management to know the satisfaction level of employees and they can take measure to increase productivity.
- This study focus on effectiveness and employee attitude of the training system.

1.3 LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

- Due to restriction to enter into some of the departments 21 SREE VIDHYA RUBBER PVT. LTD. I could not cover some of the nepocts required for my study.
- Interaction with the company executive was limited due to their busy schedule.
- The information collected is mainly primary data and the accurney os subject to the responses received.
- The employees of the SREE VIDHYA RUBBER PVT LTD. Services found it difficul to answer questions properly due to their busy and heavy workload.
- The total time allowed by company to do the project was very less.
- Being a very lengthy and complex process it is difficult to analyse the details of training and process.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

According to Davenport (2006), mentioned in his recent studies that it's easy to implement strategy with the internet supported software. Technical training is the process of teaching employees how to more accurately and thoroughly perform the technical components of their jobs. Training can include technology applications, products, sales and service tactics, and more Technical skills are job - specific as opposed to soft skills, which are transferable.

Although this area of training effectiveness seems paramount, and although training is an integral part of the employer - employee relationship. **Knoke and Kalleberg (1994)** suggest direct evidence about company training practices based on representative samples of diverse employing

organizations is almost non-existent. Furthermore, several authors have suggested that training is most extensive only in establishments which operate in complex market environments **Rowden & Conine, 2005; Sahinidis & Bouris, (2008).**

In addition, **Rowden and Conine (2005)** indicate that there is limited research on human resource development in small and mid-sized businesses. According to these authors, most people believe that small businesses do little, if any, development of their workers, which annually conducts research on the training industry in the United States, as not even attempting to contact businesses with fewer than 100 employees.

Cheng and Ho (2001) also discuss the importance of training and its impact on job performance. While employee performance is one of the crucial measures emphasized by the top management, employees are more concerned about their own productivity and are increasingly aware of the accelerated obsolescence of knowledge and skills in their turbulent environment. As the literature suggests, by effectively training and developing employees, they will become more aligned for career growth - career potential enhances personal motivation.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This chapter on research methodology took a look at the research background, research design, population, sampling technique, sampling size, data collection procedure and data analysis.

3.1 RESEARCH DESIGN

Descriptive research design is used in this study.

3.2 POPULATION OF THE STUDY

The population of the study consists of 200 employees.

3.3 SAMPLING TECHNIQUE

The purposive (also known as judgmental or subjective) sampling technique was used in the sampling process of the population of the research.

3.4 SAMPLE SIZE

The sample size of the study is 100 employees.

3.5 DATA COLLECTION

For the purpose of the study, the necessary data has been collected from primary and secondary sources.

- **Primary Data:** Primary Data are collected by using questionnaires. The questionnaire was prepared mainly to know employee welfare facilities in the organization.
- **Secondary Data:** Secondary Data means data that is already available; the data is taken from annual reports and organizational profiles.

3.6 TOOLS FOR ANALYSIS

Analysis means extracting meaningful information from the data collected by analysing the information statistically. The collected data were analysed with the help of

1. Simple Percentage Analysis

PERCENTAGE ANALYSIS

Percentage method was extensively used for findings various details. It is used for making comparison between two or more service of data. The percentage analysis is used to calculate the percentage of the favourable and unfavourable responses. It can be calculate,

$$\text{Percentage (No of response / No of total response) * 100}$$

4. DATA ANALYSIS & INTERPRETATION

TABLE 4.1 SHOWING EXPERIENCE OF RESPONDENTS

Sl.NO	Options	No.Of respondents	Percentage
1	Below 1 year	5	5%
2	1-2 years	26	26%
3	2-4 years	43	43%
4	4-6 years	24	24%
5	Above 6 years	2	2%
Total		100	100%

Source: Survey data

CHART 4.1.SHOWING EXPERIENCE OF RESPONDENTS

INTERPRETATION

From the above table-4,4 it can observe that 5% of respondents are below 1 year experience in the organization and 26% of respondents are 1-2 years experience in the organization and whereas 43% of respondents are 2-4 years experience and 24% of respondents are 4-6 years in the organization. 2% of respondents are above 6 years experience.

neutral.

TABLE 4.2.RESPONDENTS OPINION ON EFFECTIVENESS OF TRAINING

Sl.No	Options	No.Of respondents	Percentage
1	Strongly Agree	49	49%
2	Agree	0	0%
3	Neutral	7	7%
4	Disagree	44	44%
5	Strongly Disagree	0	0%
Total		100	100%

Source: Survey data

CHART 4.2. RESPONDENTS OPINION ON EFFECTIVENESS OF TRAINING

INTERPRETATION

From the above table-4.7 it can observe that 49% of respondents are strongly agree the training program, 7% of respondents are neutral the training program, 44% of respondents are disagree.

TABLE 4.3 RESPONDENTS OPINION ON DEVELOPMENT ACTIVITY HELPS THE MANAGEMENT

Sl.NO	Options	No.Of respondents	Percentage
1	Strongly Agree	14	14%
2	Agree	70	70%
3	Neutral	10	10%
4	Disagree	6	6%
5	Strongly Disagree	0	0%
Total		100	100%

Source: Survey data

CHART 3 RESPONDENTS OPINION ON DEVELOPMENT ACTIVITY HELPS THE MANAGEMENT

INTERPRETATION

From the above table-4.17 it can observe that 14% of respondents are strongly agree, 70% of respondents are agree, 10% of respondents are neutral, 6% of respondents are disagree.

5. FINDINGS

- Most of the respondents were agreed with the training program is compulsory for all the employees through training.
- Mon of the respondents were agreed with the employees attend training programs regularly through training.
- Most of the respondents were agreed with the art is regularly organized for employees through training

6. SUGGESTIONS

- 1. The result of the training program also should be analyzed and training should be arranged periodically
- 2. The management may improve and conduct more training program by identifying the performance level of each individual
- 3. Company has introduce effective training in every department of the firm so as to learn more knowledge in the subject
- 4. Give computer based training to employees once in every three mentis.

- 5. On the job training and off the job training is equally important. Provide both the training continually to the employees
- 6. Provide employees motivation program and offer training program for the development towards profit making.

7. CONCLUSION

The study of training and development of employees at SREE VIDHYA RUBBER PVT Lid. In order to increase productivity the industry required to provide good training to all workers like technical training, management training, technical skill, presentation skill, soft skill training The management may give more training programmes by identifying the employees performance level of each individual. It can be concluded that the employees training provided by the company is satisfactory.

8. REFERENCES

1. Armstrong, M. (2020). *Armstrong's Handbook of Human Resource Management Practice* (15th ed.). Kogan Page.
2. Noe, R. A. (2017). *Employee Training and Development* (7th ed.). McGraw-Hill Education.
3. Decenzo, D. A., Robbins, S. P., & Verhulst, S. L. (2016). *Human Resource Management* (12th ed.). Wiley India.
4. Goldstein, I. L., & Ford, J. K. (2002). *Training in Organizations: Needs Assessment, Development, and Evaluation* (4th ed.). Wadsworth/Thomson Learning.
5. Khan, R. A. G., Khan, F. A., & Khan, M. A. (2011). *Impact of training and development on organizational performance*. *Global Journal of Management and Business Research*, 11(7), 63–68.
6. Pattanayak, B. (2020). *Human Resource Management* (6th ed.). PHI Learning Pvt. Ltd.